

ATTRIBUTES OF THE CRIMINAL COPYRIGHT INFRINGEMENT PHENOMENON

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Abstract: *Copyright protection is essential for creativity, competition, and economic development. This article discusses aspects regarding the infringement of copyright from the criminal law perspective. The article explains the need for effective criminal provisions and, based on the content analysis of a comprehensive corpus of data, consisting of cases brought to United States Courts, law enforcement press releases, and intellectual property agencies and industry groups reports, identifies, analyzes, and groups the attributes of the phenomenon under four main categories: type of works infringed, methods of infringement, enforcement aspects, and loss. The article concludes with implications and potential uses of the findings.*

Keywords: *copyright; criminal infringement; attribute; unauthorized use; illicit streaming*

I. Introduction

Copyright protection is essential for creativity, competition, and economic development. However, protected works, through a variety of business models, such as embedded streaming, peer-to-peer communities, or TV gateways, on the Internet or on the Darknet, are infringed globally on a massive scale.¹ Even though recent studies show a decrease of the online infringement of copyright,² the phenomenon remains a major concern for stakeholders, as it causes notable decreases in sales, increases the costs associated with rights enforcement and legal assistance, diminishes the possibility or incentives to produce new creative content, and undermines the business goodwill.

The enforcing of copyright comprises a number of approaches and mechanisms. This article discusses the enforcement of copyright from the criminal law perspective and is structured as follows. Part II outlines the main protection mechanisms and underlines the need for criminal

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¹ See Amy Watson, *Number of media piracy site visits worldwide 2018, by country*, STATISTA (May 27, 2019), <https://www.statista.com/statistics/786046/media-piracy-site-visits-by-country/> (the U.S. had the highest number visits to piracy sites in 2018: 17.38 billion); Daniela Coppola, *Number of cases of copyright infringements in media industry in Italy between 2014 and 2019*, STATISTA (Aug. 5, 2019), <https://www.statista.com/statistics/882833/copyright-infringements-in-media-industry-in-italy/>; C. Textor, *Number of copyright law violation cases in Taiwan 2009-2018*, STATISTA (Jan. 23, 2020), <https://www.statista.com/statistics/937843/taiwan-number-copyright-law-violation-cases/> (in Taiwan, in 2018, were registered 2,776 cases of copyright infringement).

² European Union Intellectual Property Office, *Online copyright infringement in the European Union music, films and TV (2017-2018), trends and drivers* (2019) (showing a decrease in access to pirated movies and music); João Pedro Quintais & Joost Poort, *The Decline of Online Piracy: How Markets - Not Enforcement - Drive Down Copyright Infringement*, 34 AM. U. INT'L L. REV.807 (2019) (showing a decline of online piracy).

provisions. Part III, based on a comprehensive corpus of data, consisting of cases brought to U.S. Courts, law enforcement press releases, and intellectual property agencies and industry groups reports, describes the main attributes of the criminal copyright infringement phenomenon. The article concludes with implications and potential uses of the findings.

II. Copyright Protection

Copyright is a private right, and the enforcement of the copyright is essentially the responsibility of the copyright holder. To enforce their exclusive rights, owners, as applicable to their works, can resort to technology, contractual provisions, license agreements, and civil remedies.

Technological protection measures (TPM) and rights management information (RMI). Technology, such as blockchain, can also be used to track down copyrighted works. The holders of the rights in protected works can also impose contractual obligations or require Internet service providers (ISPs) and other intermediaries to play an enforcement role, through algorithmic enforcement³ (to filter out, block, or delete infringing contents) or via “notice and takedown” procedures.

Online community norms⁴ or contractual terms for consumers, normally set in end user licensing agreement (EULA) and/or terms of use (ToU), which prohibit licensees from a number of actions, such as the distribution, the reproduction, the transmission, the sale, or the licensing of the protected work, are also used to delineate permitted forms of use, sharing, or reselling.

When their rights are infringed, copyright owners can seek remedies through civil suits,⁵ by requesting orders to prevent violations (for instance, blocking, live, or de-indexing injunctions) and claims for damages. However, rights holders often lack the necessary resources to effectively address infringements through civil actions. Moreover, civil actions could alienate consumers, and are “unlikely to yield the copyright holder the full amount of awarded damages.”⁶

Apart from the infringement of the exclusive rights of creators, the copyright infringement phenomenon also raises serious cybersecurity concerns: under the lure of free works, offenders can expose victims to fraud, identity theft, unwanted ads, or other harms, such as malware infection.⁷ Further, a number of these schemes are perpetrated in connection with other offenses, often employ sophisticated means, such as reverse proxy or other party linking (deep-linking, framing, inline linking, or embedded linking), with a view to mask the host of the infringing activity, or the use of fictitious entities or offshore accounts, and may involve other aspects, such as the extradition of perpetrators. Consequently, there is a clear need to impose criminal measures against copyright infringements.

Criminal measures are also required for compliance with Art. 61 of the TRIPS Agreement (“Members shall provide for criminal procedures and penalties to be applied at least in cases of [...]

³ See Maayan Perel & Niva Elkin-Koren, *Accountability in Algorithmic Copyright Enforcement*, 19 STAN. TECH. L. REV. 473 (2016).

⁴ See Julia Bauer, Nikolaus Franke & Philipp Tuertscher, *Intellectual Property Norms in Online Communities: How User-Organized Intellectual Property Regulation Supports Innovation*, 27 INFORMATION SYSTEMS RESEARCH 724 (2016).

⁵ See 17 U.S.C. § 411.

⁶ Geraldine Szott Moohr, *Defining Overcriminalization Through Cost-Benefit Analysis: The Example of Criminal Copyright Laws*, 54 AM. U. L. REV. 783, 799 (2005).

⁷ See a discussion on the nexus between copyright infringement and malware in *2019 Review of Notorious Markets for Counterfeiting and Piracy*, OFFICE OF THE UNITED STATES TRADE REPRESENTATIVE (2019).

copyright piracy on a commercial scale”) and Art. 10 of the Council of Europe Convention on Cybercrime (CETS No. 185) of 2001 (“Each Party shall adopt such legislative and other measures as may be necessary to establish as criminal offences under its domestic law the infringement of copyright”).

Criminal copyright infringement can take numerous forms, reflected in the comprehensive national legal frameworks. For illustration, in the U.S., offenses under copyright law include the infringement of copyright for profit or without a profit motive; the pre-release distribution of a copyrighted work over publicly accessible computer networks; the circumvention of copyright protection systems; the unauthorized fixation of and the trafficking in of sound recordings and music videos of live musical performances; and the unauthorized recording of motion pictures in exhibition facilities.⁸ In Singapore, offenses under copyright law include the manufacture of infringing copies for commercial purposes; the sale of infringing copies of protected works; the possession, importation, or distribution of infringing copies for commercial purposes.⁹

In Spain, the crimes relating to copyright include the reproduction, distribution, plagiarism, or public disclosure of a protected work, without authorization from the holder of the rights; actively and in a non-neutral manner, providing access or enabling, without the authorization of the rights holder, the identification on the Internet of protected works; the export or storing of copies of protected works, without authorization, with the intention to reproduce, distribute, or publicly disclose them; the promotion or facilitation of access to protected works through the elimination or modification, without authorization from the rights holder, of TPM; the manufacturing or possession for commercial purposes of means that facilitates unauthorized suppression or neutralization of technical devices used to protect copyrighted works.¹⁰

III. Phenomenon Attributes¹¹

Criminal copyright infringement is a complex phenomenon, which can involve cyberspace and/or physical components. This part analyzes the following high-level attributes of the phenomenon: type of works infringed, methods of infringement, enforcement aspects, and loss. As suggested by the content analyses on the corpus of data used, several sub-categories are identified and discussed.

Digital technology allows offenders to place numerous types of illegally copied (pirated) content on different platforms and markets. The survey of cases shows that works most often infringed are computer programs, musical works, motion pictures, and television programs. Other works, such as books or pictorial works, are also infringed, however, on a smaller scale.

The most important rights infringed in criminal cases are the reproduction and the distribution rights. Depending on the type of work infringed, the content can be obtained or reproduced through illegal copying; unauthorized use; unauthorized stream ripping sites;¹² via pirate sites;¹³

⁸ See an extended discussion in Ioana VasIU & Lucian VasIU, *Criminal Copyright Infringement: Forms, Extent, and Prosecution in the United States*, 4 UNIVERSITY OF BOLOGNA LAW REVIEW 229, 244-6 (2019).

⁹ INTELLECTUAL PROPERTY OFFICE OF SINGAPORE, <https://www.ipos.gov.sg/understanding-innovation-ip/copyright/criminal-offences>.

¹⁰ Iban Díez & Jaime Bello, *Copyright litigation in Spain: overview*, THOMSON REUTERS (2020).

¹¹ An early version of the descriptive part of this section was included, in a different form, in *Criminal Copyright Infringement*, *supra* note 8.

¹² E.g., YouTube-mp3.org, a very large site that offered illegal “stream ripped” music, *see World’s largest music stream ripping site shuts down after successful international legal action from record industry*, RIAA (2017),

theft of television signal;¹⁴ unauthorized decryption of premium TV channels;¹⁵ bootlegging;¹⁶ etc. The distribution vectors include selling counterfeited copies¹⁷ or illegally reproduced works at flea markets;¹⁸ warehouse for the dissemination of counterfeited copies;¹⁹ counterfeit work sold online;²⁰ replication plants;²¹ etc.

The numerous copyright infringement methods also include the use of “key generators;”²² eBay selling of pirated software;²³ trading of unauthorized product key cards;²⁴ dissemination of unauthorized re-installation disks;²⁵ file-sharing;²⁶ etc.

Online platforms, such as video sharing platforms (VSP) and Internet marketplace websites, are also often actively used by perpetrators in the infringing activity: for instance, illegal streaming of copyrighted works on Jetflix;²⁷ illegally uploading of movies, prior to their official release in cinemas;²⁸ illegal posting of films on Facebook;²⁹ selling of unauthorized copies on Amazon;³⁰ etc.

Advanced technologies are used to provide large scale access to infringed works, often for significant monetary gain: for example, Internet Protocol Television (IPTV) services;³¹ linking

<https://www.riaa.com/worlds-largest-music-stream-ripping-site-shuts-successful-international-legal-action-record-industry/>.

¹³ See *Eight Defendants Charged with Running Two of the Largest Illegal Television Show and Movie Streaming Services in the United States*, U.S. DEP’T OF JUSTICE (Aug. 27, 2019), <https://www.justice.gov/opa/pr/eight-defendants-charged-running-two-largest-illegal-television-show-and-movie-streaming> (through sophisticated computer programs, the defendants allegedly scoured pirate sites for content, then made the content available on servers to subscribers for streaming and/or downloading).

¹⁴ The illegal tapping of cable TV systems and satellite signals, without authorization, see Hedi Nasheri, *Addressing Global Scope of Intellectual Property Law* (2005) at 18.

¹⁵ See *United States v. Manzer*, 69 F.3d 222 (8th Cir. 1995).

¹⁶ *United States v. Armstead*, 524 F.3d 442, 443 (4th Cir. 2008).

¹⁷ *Jury Convicts Man for Counterfeiting More Than 48,000 DVDs*, U.S. NEWS & WORLD REPORT (2019), <https://www.usnews.com/news/best-states/maine/articles/2019-10-30/jury-convicts-man-for-counterfeiting-more-than-48-000-dvds>.

¹⁸ *United States v. Frison*, 825 F.3d 437 (8th Cir. 2016).

¹⁹ Press Release, U.S. DEP’T OF JUSTICE, *Three Indicted for Criminal Copyright Infringement* (Mar 21, 2013), <https://archives.fbi.gov/archives/sacramento/press-releases/2013/three-indicted-for-criminal-copyright-infringement>.

²⁰ *United States v. Kononchuk*, 485 F.3d 199 (3d Cir. 2007).

²¹ *United States v. Liu*, 731 F.3d 982 (9th Cir. 2013).

²² *United States v. Anderson*, 741 F.3d 938 (9th Cir. 2013).

²³ *United States v. Fair*, 699 F.3d 508 (D.C. Cir. 2012).

²⁴ Press Release, U.S. DEP’T OF JUSTICE, *Florida Man Pleads Guilty to Software Piracy Scheme* (Mar 2, 2017), <https://www.justice.gov/usao-wdmo/pr/florida-man-pleads-guilty-software-piracy-scheme>.

²⁵ *United States v. Lundgren*, No. 17-12466, Non-Argument Calendar (11th Cir. Apr. 11, 2018).

²⁶ *Capitol Records, Inc. v. Thomas-Rasset*, 692 F.3d 899 (8th Cir. 2012).

²⁷ *United States v. Dallmann*, Criminal No. 19-cr-253 (E.D. Va. Jan. 15, 2020).

²⁸ Press Release, U.S. DEP’T OF JUSTICE, *Lancaster Man Admits Illegally Uploading Screeners of ‘The Revenant’ and ‘The Peanuts Movie’ to BitTorrent Website* (Feb 26, 2016), <https://www.justice.gov/usao-cdca/pr/lancaster-man-admits-illegally-uploading-screeners-revenant-and-peanuts-movie>.

²⁹ Press Release, U.S. DEP’T OF JUSTICE, *Fresno Man Arrested on Federal Copyright Violations for Alleged Illegal Upload of ‘Deadpool’ Movie to the Internet* (Jun 13, 2017), <https://www.justice.gov/usao-cdca/pr/fresno-man-arrested-federal-copyright-violations-alleged-illegal-upload-deadpool-movie>.

³⁰ *United States v. Vampire Nation*, 451 F.3d 189 (3d Cir. 2006).

³¹ For illustration, in the E.U., in 2018, the total revenue for illegal IPTV services was €941.7 million, while these services were used by 13.7 million people, see EUROPEAN UNION INTELLECTUAL PROPERTY OFFICE, *Illegal IPTV in the European Union* (2019) at 9.

and streaming websites; direct download cyberlockers and illicit streaming devices (ISDs) and services;³² file swapping services,³³ P2P networks³⁴ and BitTorrent portals.

The infringing activity can take very concerning forms. For instance, Megaupload, a very large conspiracy, had “more than one billion visitors in its history.”³⁵ Another compelling example is Operation D-Elite, which had over 133,000 members, which illegally distribution thousands of protected works, with a total of over 2 million downloads.³⁶ These offenses can also involve large scale money laundering,³⁷ transborder aspects,³⁸ racketeering conspiracy,³⁹ or distribution of illicit content.⁴⁰

Massive copyright infringement requires providers of hosting services. These providers can facilitate the hiding of sites behind content delivery networks (CDN). Perpetrators, in order to conceal the illegal activity, or to decrease the likelihood of detection, often employ deception mechanism, such as server movement; exclusion of infringing files from certain lists; creation of fake accounts, to upload files, so that these would look as uploaded by users, not by the conspirators; and third party linking and “referrer” websites.

For illustration, in one of the most prominent cases, the conspirators operated KAT, which facilitated the online distribution and reproduction of protected works.⁴¹ In order to circumvent seizures and civil liability, the servers of this conspiracy were moved worldwide.⁴² As part of their operations concealment, the defendants operated the scheme under firm from Ukraine.⁴³

The online infringement often involves activities and offenders that are located in other jurisdictions. This fact sometimes raises extradition, for instance, the case of Dotcom, the leader of the Mega Conspiracy,⁴⁴ still pending in New Zealand, seven years after his arrest,⁴⁵ or Batato, the marketing manager in the same conspiracy.⁴⁶

Criminal infringement of protected works can be a very lucrative business for offenders, causing high losses to the victims: \$6.3 billion in the Sharebeast scheme;⁴⁷ over \$500 million in

³² For instance, for illegally streamed copyrighted sporting telecasts, see U.S. IMMIGRATION AND CUSTOMS ENFORCEMENT, *Website Operator Indicted for Illegally Streaming Copyrighted Sporting Events* (2011), <https://www.ice.gov/news/releases/website-operator-indicted-illegally-streaming-copyrighted-sporting-events>.

³³ See *In re Aimster Copyright Litigation*, 334 F.3d 643 (7th Cir. 2003).

³⁴ See Neil Fried, *Comments of the Motion Picture Association of America, Inc.*, In the Matter of Competition and Consumer Protection in the 21st Century, Hearing 4: Oct. 23-24, 2018.

³⁵ See Indictment at 2, *United States v. Dotcom*, No. 1:12CR3 (E.D. Va. Jan. 5, 2012).

³⁶ Press Release, U.S. DEP'T OF JUSTICE, *Federal Law Enforcement Announces Operation D-Elite, Crackdown on P2P Piracy Network* (May 25, 2005), http://www.usdoj.gov/opa/pr/2005/May/05_crm_291.htm.

³⁷ See *United States v. Vaulin*, No. 16 CR 438-1 (N.D. Ill. Aug. 4, 2017); Indictment, *United States v. Dotcom*, No. 1:12CR3 (E.D. Va. Jan. 5, 2012); *United States v. Dallmann*, Criminal No. 19-cr-253 (E.D. Va. Jan. 15, 2020).

³⁸ See *United States v. Batato*, 833 F.3d 413 (4th Cir. 2016).

³⁹ See *United States v. All Assets Listed in Attachment A*, 89 F. Supp. 3d 813 (E.D. Va. 2015) (in violation of 18 U.S.C. § 1962(d)).

⁴⁰ See Indictment at 11, *United States v. Dotcom*, No. 1:12CR3 (E.D. Va. Jan. 5, 2012).

⁴¹ *United States v. Vaulin*, No. 16 CR 438-1 (N.D. Ill. Aug. 4, 2017).

⁴² *Id.*

⁴³ *Id.*

⁴⁴ Indictment at 13, *United States v. Dotcom*, No. 1:12CR3 (E.D. Va. Jan. 5, 2012).

⁴⁵ Melissa Nightingale, *Kim Dotcom extradition legal battle in Supreme Court coming to an end*, NZ Herald (Jun. 17, 2019), https://www.nzherald.co.nz/nz/news/article.cfm?c_id=1&objectid=12241050.

⁴⁶ *Megaupload extradition: Finn Batato finally appoints lawyer* (Jun 13, 2019), <http://www.scoop.co.nz/stories/HL1906/S00046/megaupload-extradition-finn-batato-finally-appoints-lawyer.htm>.

⁴⁷ Press Release, U.S. DEP'T OF JUSTICE, *Owner of Sharebeast.com sentenced for copyright infringement* (Mar 22, 2018), <https://www.justice.gov/usao-ndga/pr/owner-sharebeastcom-sentenced-copyright-infringement>.

the Mega Conspiracy;⁴⁸ over \$100 million in a piracy scheme;⁴⁹ etc. In the U.S., the amount of loss is calculated differently for sentencing and restitution purposes. Successful claimants obtain actual damages for the losses incurred or recover statutory damages.

Table 1 summarizes the attributes discussed above.

Table 1 - Criminal Copyright Infringement Attributes

Type of work infringed	Computer Program			
	Musical Work			
	Motion Picture			
	TV Program			
	Other			
Method of infringement	Reproduction	Copying	Electronic	
			Physical	
		Unauthorized use		
		Ripping		
		Theft of signal		
		TPM Bypass		
		Bootlegging		
	Other			
	Distribution	Cyberspace	Uploading Posting	Facebook
				Cyberlocker
				Other
			Streaming	
			Linking	
			Swapping/Sharing	
		Physical	Sale	Amazon
				eBay
			Other	
			Flea market	
	Warehouse			
	Other			
Enforcement aspects	Conspiracy			
	Concealment			
	Money Laundering			
	Extradition			
	Other			
Loss	Restitution			
	Sentencing			

⁴⁸ United States v. Batato, 833 F.3d 413 (4th Cir. 2016) (the reported income exceeding \$175 million).

⁴⁹ Press Release, U.S. DEP'T OF JUSTICE, *Six Defendants Plead Guilty to \$100 Million Software Piracy Scheme* (Dec 17, 2015), <https://www.justice.gov/usao-wdmo/pr/six-defendants-plead-guilty-100-million-software-piracy-scheme>.

IV. Conclusion

The criminal copyright infringement is a widespread, multi-faceted phenomenon, causing significant negative direct and indirect consequences for stakeholders. This article discussed the rationale for the criminal protection of copyright and analyzed the main characteristics or distinctive elements of the phenomenon.

The findings of this article and the table devised could be used to improve the protection of copyright in a number of ways: to analyze or assess the effectiveness of the current legal framework; to develop educational materials; to improve the prevention policies or mechanisms; in conjunction with cost-benefit analysis (CBA) tools, to prioritize the enforcement efforts and efficiently allocate resources; and to encode and report offenses.